

Promoting excellence through research assessment reforms

Workshop Report of the CoARA National Chapter Germany – June 2026

Excellence as a systemic attribute

Excellence in research is a central principle that guides funding decisions, hiring and promotions, as well as institutional strategies. Nevertheless, the concept remains elusive. If research quality is understood as a continuum, excellence appears as the highest end of a multidimensional quality scale of research. At the same time, excellence cannot be reduced to output-based metrics or productivity and may only become apparent over longer periods of time, thereby calling into question research assessment systems that prioritize short-term research outputs and easily quantifiable results.

From the perspective of the German National Chapter of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)), **excellence should be understood as a systemic attribute**, which is fostered by the interplay of qualified personnel, supportive organizational structures, and appropriate framework conditions. It is multidimensional and context-dependent and can manifest itself at both the individual and institutional levels. At the same time, excellence is not a static quality but a social attribution that must be continuously renegotiated. The term should therefore neither be equated with exclusivity nor used inflationarily.

This workshop report was produced in the context of the meeting of [the CoARA National Chapter Germany](#) on October 10, 2025. During the workshop, participants addressed the following questions: (1) What characteristics distinguish excellent research? (2) What framework conditions must be met for excellent research? (3) How do CoARA's principles promote excellence?

Characteristics of excellent research

Excellent research is characterized by several key features that manifest themselves at different levels. Some of these features are measurable, while others are only quantifiable to a limited extent. In particular, the following features were identified and discussed in the workshop:

- **Advancement of the state of research:** Excellent research contributes to the advancement of existing knowledge by further developing or re-establishing theories, strengthening empirical foundations, and expanding the information base of a field.
- **Relevance:** Excellent research is significant within the research community and/or in

a societal context and addresses relevant questions that contribute to the further development of research and society.

- **Innovation:** Excellent research breaks new ground in terms of research questions, theoretical approaches, or methodological strategies, thereby opening up new perspectives and pathways for knowledge generation.
- **Adherence to and further development of standards:** Excellent research meets established research standards and productively advances them. This includes, in particular, robust documentation, reproducibility, and ensuring connectivity within specific disciplines as well as inter- or transdisciplinary research fields.

Supportive framework conditions for excellent research

Excellence is fundamentally enabled and promoted by institutional and research policy conditions. Among the most important supportive framework conditions are:

- **Freedom of research:** Freedom in research and teaching forms the foundation of research excellence. It enables researchers to choose research questions independently, develop methods freely, and publish results without undue influence.
- **Sustainable funding:** Long-term, stable, transparent, and equitably distributed funding ensures the continuity of projects, supports investments in high-quality infrastructure, and enables innovative and high-risk research.
- **Appropriate incentive structures:** Assessment and incentive systems should be designed to suit the specific context and take into account different disciplines, career stages, and forms of research.
- **Inclusive research cultures:** Excellence often arises from collaborative processes that bring together diverse perspectives, methods, and expertise. This opens up new pathways for knowledge generation and creates space for creative and interdisciplinary approaches.
- **Diverse and stable career paths:** Opportunities for a variety of long-term positions beyond traditional roles—including, for example, technical staff, data managers, and research managers—strengthen collective performance and institutional memory.
- **Robust research infrastructure:** Access to technological platforms, data and information systems, computing resources, and modern laboratory and infrastructure equipment enables the conduct of excellent research.
- **Supportive organizational structures:** Service-oriented and streamlined processes reduce bureaucracy, accelerate decision-making, and alleviate the administrative burden on researchers at all stages of scientific work—from proposal submission through implementation to documentation and reporting.

Quality-based assessment systems promote excellence

Traditional research assessment systems often rely on quantitative indicators such as the number of publications and the journal impact factor. These parameters not only suggest a supposed objectivity and comparability of research results but also create problematic incentives: They favor short-term productivity, prioritize quantity over quality, and undervalue central yet less visible contributions. As a result, they fail to do justice to the understanding of research excellence that underpins this approach.

Instead of compromising on excellence, initiatives such as the **Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)** promote excellence through more qualitative and comprehensive approaches, supported by a broader information base. Among the most important contributions of these research assessment reforms to excellence are the promotion of:

- **Diversity of Scholarly Contributions:** The goal of these reforms is to recognize a broader range of scholarly contributions. In addition to traditional research publications, this includes data, software, and methods publications, contributions to societal impact, as well as fundamental academic activities such as peer review, teaching, mentoring, knowledge transfer, and research support. Overall, this strengthens the multidimensional nature of excellence, ensuring that all relevant dimensions of excellence in research can be systematically taken into account.
- **Quality over quantity:** By prioritizing the significance, rigor, and creativity of research over purely output-based metrics, the reforms reduce publication pressure and promote diverse forms of scientific work—from “slow science” to application-oriented research with shorter innovation cycles.
- **Collaboration, inter- and transdisciplinarity:** By valuing teamwork and contributions from previously undervalued roles, the reforms promote interdisciplinary collaboration. This particularly strengthens those forms of excellence based on collective knowledge production and complex problem-solving.
- **Context-sensitive assessment:** Assessment criteria can be adapted to the norms of the respective discipline, career stages, and institutional goals, recognizing that excellence takes different forms across various research fields and types. This allows for a more nuanced operationalization of excellence and a context-dependent assessment.
- **Long-term and transformative impacts:** By taking broader societal, economic, or cultural impacts into account, the reforms can strengthen research with sustainable impact, which is necessary for profound, innovative progress. This links excellence to long-term and transformative effects rather than reducing it to short-term research outputs.

Conclusion

Excellence in research is not a static achievement with a uniform assessment logic and cannot be captured solely on the basis of measurable results. By advancing research assessment—moving away from the inappropriate use of quantitative metrics toward a multidimensional understanding of research achievements—reform initiatives such as CoARA are laying the conceptual and methodological foundations for incentive systems that strengthen excellent research in all its diversity and breadth.

With the support of leading national and international funding agencies and research organizations, reforms in research assessment are already underway. **The members of the CoARA National Chapter Germany call on all stakeholders in the German research ecosystem to actively participate in the further development of research assessment systems.** By achieving a critical mass and adopting a coordinated approach, systemic reforms are made possible that align research more closely with substantively meaningful research goals rather than with narrow assessment logics. In this way, diversity, efficiency, performance, and resilience can be supported and expanded across the entire research landscape, thereby effectively promoting excellence as defined here.

The entire text of this publication—with the exception of quotations—is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license. See: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

For further information about the CoARA National Chapter Germany and contact details, see: <https://www.coara.org/national-chapters/coara-national-chapter-germany/>